

XcARet: XAI based Green Security Architecture for Resilient Open Radio Access Networks in 6G

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Abstract—The fixed security solutions and related security configurations may no longer meet the diverse requirements of 6G networks. Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture is going to be one key entry point to 6G where the direct user access is granted. O-RAN promotes the design, deployment and operation of the RAN with open interfaces and optimized by intelligent controllers. O-RAN networks are to be implemented as multi-vendor systems with interoperable components and can be programmatically optimized through centralized abstraction layer and data driven closed-loop control. However, since O-RAN contains many new open interfaces and data flows, new security issues may emerge. Providing the recommendations for dynamic security policy adjustments by considering the energy availability and risk or security level of the network is something lacking in the current state-of-the-art. When the security process is managed and executed in an autonomous way, it must also assure the transparency of the security policy adjustments and provide the reasoning behind the adjustment decisions to the interested parties whenever needed. Moreover, the energy consumption for such security solutions are constantly bringing overhead to the networking devices. Therefore, in this paper we discuss XAI based green security architecture for resilient open radio access networks in 6G known as XcARet for providing cognitive and transparent security solutions for O-RAN in a more energy efficient manner.

Index Terms—O-RAN, explainability, security, energy efficiency, 6G

I. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation (6G) of wireless cellular networks has a vision of providing connectivity to all while becoming a pervasive and flexible computing-connectivity platform, supporting a dynamic establishment of heterogeneous, on-demand services involving humans, devices, and things in a sustainable manner [1]. This grand vision necessitates changes of the architectural principles on the system level, enabling an autonomous and opportunistic service construction and real-time network optimization. It is foreseen that Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) as the novel paradigm for the RAN of the future and a compelling element in 6G wireless ecosystems [2]. O-RAN promotes the RAN design, deployment and operations with open interfaces which are further optimized by intelligent controllers.

As shown in Figure 1, O-RAN architecture is comprised of radio and management components running with support of multiple control loops. O-RAN architecture has data-driven control with RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) which operate under near-real-time (10 ms to 1s) and non-real-time (more than 1s) time scales. Two RICs process the data received

from infrastructure, devices, users or radio management units and leverage AI/ML algorithms to govern and apply control policies and actions on the RAN. A full description of each functional unit in O-RAN architecture can be found in [3].

Fig. 1: Logical architecture of O-RAN with functional blocks [3].

O-RAN networks can be implemented as multi-vendor systems with interoperable components and can be programmatically optimized through data driven closed-loop control with the centralized abstraction layer. The world-wide community of O-RAN Alliance is formed with renowned mobile operators, vendors and research/academic institutes operating in RAN industry [3]. O-RAN has been formed by merging xRAN forum and Cloud RAN (C-RAN) alliance to define the requirements and specifications of O-RAN architecture.

The key property of O-RAN deployment is the disaggregated system where virtualized and softwarized components are connected via open and standardized interfaces that allow the interoperability between different vendors [4]. Both virtualization and disaggregation will pave the way towards cloud-native deployments which will further increase the reconfigurability and resilience of the RAN architecture. The open and standardized interfaces will allow telecom operators to trade

with multiple equipment vendors and even small players will get a chance to be onboarded in the RAN ecosystem.

There are many interesting research works going on O-RAN in different aspects including resource allocation, energy efficiency, architecture, test bed implementation and evaluation. Security is another key consideration in O-RAN although it has not yet gained the sufficient attention from the research community. Security must be considered in societal, economic, and environmental sustainability. When the security solutions or security configurations are energy consuming it is always important to monitor them and adjust them according to the risk level or the impact of the threat to the entire life cycle of the system in an intelligent way. Majority of the present-day security solutions are formed as static solutions with static configuration. For instance, when the RAN devices from different vendors are connecting to O-RAN, they may come with pre-set security configurations. However, when the devices are in operation, based on the usecase and the user security requirements defined in Service Level Agreement (SLA), there are certain instances where the desired level of security may vary.

Providing the recommendations for dynamic adjustments in security policies with considering the energy availability and the risk level of the network is something lacking in the current state-of-the-art. At the same time, when the process is adjusted in an autonomous way, and it must assure the transparency of the adjustment of those security policies and reason out the interested parties whenever needed. In this paper we provide our insights about the so called XcARet solution which describes an explainable AI (XAI) based green security architecture for resilient O-RAN in 6G. Here we discuss how to provide energy profiling for security operations in O-RAN with the added intelligence and explainability. Thereby, we present our view on establishing more sustainable security solutions for O-RAN ecosystem.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses the O-RAN architecture, security threats and security specifications in the current state-of-the-art. Section III discusses the key design principles of XcARet. Section IV gives some insights about how to accomplish energy profiling for O-RAN security. Section V describes how to utilize XAI techniques to improve O-RAN security with explainability. Section VI and Section VII respectively present the definitions for green security and sustainable security in O-RAN. Finally, Section VIII draws some concluding remarks followed by the future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND OF O-RAN SECURITY

The introduction of new architectural components, open interfaces and data driven closed loop operations may bring unprecedented security challenges with O-RAN. Recently, O-RAN Security Focus Group (WG11) in O-RAN Alliance has defined a list of security stakeholders, threat landscape and security requirements [5]. Similar to other 6G technologies, AI/ML security threats are intuitively applicable to O-RAN operations. The threats against O-RAN architecture are mainly

identified in terms of O-RAN system, virtualization environment (O-Cloud), open-source code, physical infrastructure or hardware, wireless functionalities and AI/ML components and data pipelines. Among them, the most appealing one is the threat against AI/ML models which are used for inference and control in xApps and rApps respectively operating in near-RT RIC and non-RT RIC. It is important to keep the focus on developing security solutions for the threats against AI/ML models used in the O-RAN architecture and how to apply them in the operations of non-RT RIC to bring intelligent and trustworthy operations in the management process of security service level agreements (SSLAs). More importantly when dealing with the meeting points of O-RAN architecture with the human-centric networks, it is significant to provide the understanding of particular security solutions as well as the operations performed during the management process. Table I summarizes the possible threat scenarios in O-RAN ecosystem.

As highlighted in EU O-RAN security report [6], while setting up zero-touch management in O-RAN with a zero trust mind set, it is important for mobile network operators (MNOs) to adapt the monitoring process into a modular environment where every component is checked and monitored. However, when this process is facilitated with AI and controlled through the defined interfaces only, there can be instances where even the MNOs cannot predict the network behaviours and rectify the errors easily. In one hand, the added intelligence in O-RAN automation and management with AI/ML and data analysis, will allow the closed loop responses to control the network configurations. This will definitely reduce the human interaction and in a way reduce the threats that may occur due to human errors. On the other hand, such a fully automated network may loose the control of the MNOs over critical process with the risks in terms of liability, security and availability. However, we can reduce this risk significantly by introducing more explainability to the decisions taken by those black-box AI models running in different stages of the O-RAN management process.

European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) zero-touch network and service automation (ZSM) group is established to discover and standardize the autonomous network management using high level policy rules to enable self-configuration, self-monitoring, self-healing and self-optimization without human intervention in 5G and beyond networks [7]. There are few security architectures proposed for ZSM to assure its intelligent and trustworthy operations. These security architectures complement the security closed loop operations with multiple security and trust enablers for attack detection, limit propagation and attack mitigation, which is followed by security orchestration and re-defined security configurations based on the security policies and security SLAs (SSLAs). Typical AI/ML based security enablers are black box models where the explanations of the certain security actions are not provided to the stakeholders who are impacted by them. Besides, they do not consider the energy consumption of those security actions for decision making process. With respect to

TABLE I: Categorization of security threats related to O-RAN system

Threat category	Description of possible threat scenarios
Threats against O-RAN system	Unauthorized access to O-RAN components due to insecure design and misconfiguration of O-RAN components such as fronthaul interfaces and M-S-C-U planes, O-RU, Network Functions (NF), inter-connecting interfaces (R1, A1), SMO, Non-RT TIC (rApps), Near-RT RIC (xApps). Due to weak authentication and access control methods at the web servers serving at O-RAN network boundary.
Threats against Open Cloud	Threats concerning O-Cloud management, interfaces and hardware resources, virtualization layers, Virtual Machine (VM)/container images.
Threats due to open source code	Due to vulnerabilities in software components.
Physical threats	Security threats occurring due to intruders' physical access of O-RAN components and damage sensitive data.
Threats against 5G radio networks	Interruption in radio links due to jamming, spoofing and traffic sniffing and DoS attacks on cognitive radio networks.
Threats against AI/ML	Common AI/ML threats including data poisoning attacks, model poisoning attacks, and inference attacks.
Protocol stack threats	Threats occurring due to REST protocol stack used by A1 and R1 interfaces.

the programmable RAN, the initial step has been set by the O-RAN Alliance and O-RAN security group, breaking down the monolithic paradigm and introducing the decentralization and virtualization in RANs together with identifying attack surface and security threats. Yet, the O-RAN framework is still in the early stage, not being able to truly break the existing technological and business barriers, as well as support dynamic and automatized service construction and management. Some of the key concepts that yet must be realized in O-RAN security architecture are to assure trustworthiness in multi-tenancy, to allow energy efficient and adaptive security protocols towards green security, autonomous SSLA management for the execution of decentralized business models and real-time multi-stakeholder integration.

III. DESIGN PRINCIPLES OF XCARET

Security is a gateway to safe and resilient networks that can withstand in a hostile environment when the cyber criminals and adversaries are always intensifying their powers. Although there are many solutions proposed to make the distributed architectures secure and resilient, they have their own limitations to support the fast-growing device heterogeneity, their energy profiles, and management of security functionalities in an autonomous way. Besides, on one hand, with the current technological and societal evolution, people are keen on their own privacy, security and secure connectivity options than ever before. On the other hand, the higher levels of energy consumption have limited the incorporation of many security solutions with the devices with low power profiles. This concludes the necessity of developing more robust security solutions which can be explainable or provide a higher trustworthiness to the society and in a more energy efficient manner. Therefore, with XcARet we propose an intelligent green security architecture with the added explainability to the management of SSLAs in the O-RAN ecosystem and applicable for 6G telecommunication era.

In Figure 2, we show the key strengthening factors or the key characteristics of XcARet that include intelligence, explainability and energy efficiency. We believe, this will fulfill 6G demands to create a more trustworthy and sustainable RAN. Although O-RAN architecture is evolving in an appealing speed, security in O-RAN is still in its infancy.

Fig. 2: Characteristics of envisioned XcARet solution.

Therefore, the design and development of such a sustainable architecture will contribute with fundamental breakthroughs for future developments and standardization of O-RAN. For their part future definitions of complete and effective security recommendations will lead to the broad use of the benefits that O-RAN architecture will bring to the societies of the future.

IV. ENERGY PROFILING FOR O-RAN SECURITY

In this section we discuss how zero trust security models are compatible with the underlying concepts of O-RAN and how the energy profiles are evaluated for the security operations in the O-RAN architecture.

Since the centralized network security models are becoming more and more vulnerable, O-RAN always enforces the decentralization of the virtual aspects of the network and so as its security operations. However, since the O-RAN architecture is open to multiple interfaces and technologies, it may create increased complexity and novel vulnerabilities with security threats. Therefore, O-RAN requires a zero-trust-based security architecture to ensure resilience and security of the complex 6G ecosystem. On the other hand, with the energy consumption perspective, it is important to investigate the role of security policies and the security configuration in the O-

RAN architecture and their implication to the device energy profiles and the overall energy consumption in the network. This should also need to significantly advance 6G security vision embracing all anticipated changes whereas focusing on most pressing 6G security needs in heterogeneous and distributed ecosystems.

As the initializing phase it is important to assess the current security policy management processes and their energy profiles. The main requirement is to identify the most critical security operations and security policies that will affect the operations in O-RAN and their energy profiles (e.g., reference specifications for security protocols, security requirements, and threat modeling and remediation analysis reports [5]). For instance, we can consider the security operations perform at the non-RT RIC with a latency requirement in the range of over 1s. The operations in non-RT RIC are mainly performed by rApps, which leverage the management functionalities of the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework. In the current state-of-the-art, energy saving rApp is adapted to coordinate and evaluate the power usage of the O-RAN gNBs based on traffic loading [2].

Fig. 3: Example of rApps to perform energy profiling of security operations.

Going further in this process we are working towards developing an rApp to evaluate the energy consumption of security related tasks performed by the gNBs in correlation to the security policies and actions (i.e., attack detection, mitigation, limit of propagation, etc.). Here we will also identify how rApps can contribute to security analysis and threat identification to improve the integrity, resilience, and availability of the deployed O-RAN architecture by taking into consideration of the energy profiles associated with the different security operations.

As an example Figure 3 illustrates the organization of three rApps that can contribute for the energy profiling of security operations in O-RAN. Here, **rApp L** consumes the O1 interface to estimate the UE location and identify the possible security threats using the previous data collected in the serving/neighbouring cells. Secondly, **rApp E** measures

the power utilization measurements for the security operations, and the available amount of computation resources and energy profiles in the cells and evaluates the security risk level in the given cells. Finally, **rApp S** takes the inputs from **rApp L** and **rApp E** to provide recommendations to the dynamic security policies based required level of security and resource availability to perform the security operations.

Depending on the capabilities of the hardware platforms utilized to host the different components of the O-RAN architecture as well as the implementation of the monitoring functionalities in the O-RAN software, it is possible that not all the required information to dynamically optimize both the energy consumption and security level for the network will be directly available for the rApps listed in the example above. For example, even though the monitoring tools provided by the O-RAN and server control software would be able to provide the required details on the traffic load and available computational resources to **rApp E** when different security policies are in use, it can be that accurate measurements on the related energy consumption are not available. For this purpose, a separate energy measurement framework based on hardware energy meters can be installed in parallel with the O-RAN components to provide the missing energy consumption data for the live network. Another option is to measure the energy consumption for the different security policy, traffic load and resource consumption combinations offline and offer this information to **rApp E** as fixed input. Even if the accuracy of the offline estimate of the energy consumption for the different security configurations and network states at **rApp E** would not be on the same level with the approach based on live measurements, **rApp S** should be able to provide recommendations that benefit the overall network performance.

V. XAI FOR O-RAN SECURITY

In this section, we discuss how to formulate intelligent and trustworthy security solutions for non-RT RIC operations in O-RAN to bring intelligence and trustworthiness by using eXplainable AI (XAI) based techniques. For instance, innovative technologies such as digital twin networks (DTN) can be easily incorporate with the design, realization and maintaining functionalities of the O-RAN networks [8]. The key elements of DTN such as data, mapping, models and interfaces are necessary to relate with the physical network to achieve its analyze, diagnose, emulate and control processes. When utilizing AI training models for these processes, specially in security related actions, XAI will bring more transparency if the decisions can be analysed by humans or machinery to interact with Intent-Based Networking (IBN) for network life-cycle management. As illustrated in Figure 4 we identify the high-level incorporation of XAI for O-RAN security and use the results for improving human training as well as the machine learning model training. Here the explainability can be introduced with XAI models which can be utilized for exploring and learning methods of humans or machines and thereby modify the intents.

Fig. 4: Introducing XAI for the interaction with Network Digital Twin and real O-RAN.

If we consider more specific scenarios, there are different types of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks that can occur in an O-RAN architecture and particularly against non-RT RIC. For instance, an attacker may penetrate the non-RT RIC through AI interface or from external sources through SMO and attempt to trigger a DoS attack. False or malicious AI policies from non-RT RIC can be issued to near-RT RIC for enforcement. External parties have certain control over the network for deploying third party rApps. Thus, security architecture should be robust to counter the vulnerabilities introduced by these third party applications. Intrusion detection systems (IDS) can be used to identify the network anomalies and attack traffic. Federated Learning (FL) based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques have shown effective results for different RAN optimization operations [9]. FL techniques can be used in the security domain in a similar manner. FL security agents can be located in different locations of the network to collect data and pass those data to a trusted data collector before passing them to the inference engine.

Security measures should be designed considering the accuracy and latency requirement of the applications to be decisive in real-time [4]. Black box type AIs are promising solution to these expectations. But these black-box AIs lack the transparency in its decisions. Adversarial attacks on AI/ML models are another type of security issue that arises in an O-RAN architecture. XAI poses a great potential providing a solution to these described security challenges. Explanations are a significant factor in understanding the attack surface of adversarial machine learning [10]. XAI also improves the transparency and accountability of black-box AI models and can be used to explain any deterioration in the performance of these black-box models to proactively identify issues in the model training or issues in the data quality.

Figure 5 depicts the proposed security analytic engine at non-RT RIC to deploy and update the global FL model. Federated security agents of the network will be responsible for all the data pre-processing, training of the local FL model and ML inference to detect security incidents. Explanations for each of

the predictions are generated using XAI in the security agent. These explanations are stored in the trusted data collector and utilized by the system administrators and external parties to fine tune the life cycle of AI operations. Additionally, these explanations can be exploited in faster and efficient root cause analysis services [11], [12]. By providing explainability for security actions considered in rApps as discussed above, we implicitly assure the trustworthiness among the stakeholders in O-RAN ecosystem.

Fig. 5: Trustworthy federated O-RAN security architecture.

Typical data driven algorithms are consuming massive amount of memory and computing power. Studies have been carried out on profiling energy consumption of various XAI algorithms [13]. Hence it is vital to consider the energy efficiency of XAI integrated in O-RAN security for optimal power consumption in the network.

VI. GREEN SECURITY

Here we define green security as the security solutions or the fine-tuning of security configurations under an energy-aware perspective [14]. Game theory can be used to find the optimum security policies and manage the SLA considering the factors such as required level of security and available energy in the system. For example, running Stackelberg Security Games and AI-based joint optimization algorithms to evaluate the real-time information receiving from the network can be used for deciding the best set of actions [15]. Deep reinforcement learning based algorithms can be further used to find the best strategies that adapt the real time information regarding the energy availability, the aftereffects of attacks, required level of security, etc. For instance, the mitigation actions will be done enforcing the policies on existing security agents or deploying new security agents (e.g., IPS, firewalls, active probes) and affected functions (e.g., an infected rApp or malicious AI policy) can be cleaned and re-instantiated (with a certified-by-vendor version) to remove the problem. For the modification of policy and SLA management function, it is important to consider both the explanations received from XAI and the optimum strategies derived for green security. After that it is possible to notify the administrator and the client about the anomaly and the reactive/proactive action. If administrator or the client needs further elaboration on the new policy and

SSLA Data Services, it can provide the reasons using saved explanations. One or multiple rApps can be defined in non-RT RIC to define these functionalities derived in green security operations and make them run in the O-RAN architecture.

VII. SUSTAINABLE SECURITY FOR O-RAN

By default the notion of an open architecture coming with O-RAN brings more positive impact on the sustainability of communication networks in the journey from 5G towards 6G. The openness, intelligence, virtualization and full interoperability introduced in the O-RAN architecture, enable more efficient and effective mobile communication networks. In order to bring greater sustainability with the networks, O-RAN provides more flexibility to the operators to utilize disaggregated hardware and software components with a higher flexibility to improve cost effectiveness, energy efficiency and security.

Particularly in this paper we discuss about our vision on how to achieve sustainable security for O-RAN with the cutting edge technologies in 6G. The implementation of security measures needs to be long-lasting and adaptable to the operational environment and network state. This is the key motivation for us to bring intelligence, explainability and energy efficiency into the discussed security solutions. This will be a combination of automated security operations and improving trustworthiness in the networks while maintaining low energy profiles for the security operations whenever possible. In the long run, the energy-aware approach to security will drive towards the composition of the O-RAN ecosystem that is more sustainable and does not negatively impact the environment and society.

Finding the most feasible approach to the acquisition of the accurate energy measurement data for the rApps in different kinds of O-RAN infrastructures should be a high priority when planning the deployment of a green security framework. Depending on the scale of the deployment as well as the hardware and software used to set up the network, some of the implementation options for a live energy measurement environment could be not available or would be too expensive to realize in practice. In such cases, the option to utilize energy consumption estimates generated offline for different security configurations and network states will offer a way to include the required information into the RAN optimization decisions made by the non-RT RIC.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this paper, we discuss XcARet as a sustainable security architecture for O-RAN and how to achieve its key characteristics to improve security while considering the energy efficiency, intelligence and explainability of the related processes. Going further from the design principles and enabling technological components of XcARet architecture, in the next phase we intend to implement the energy profiling methods and XAI based security solutions to make O-RAN more resilient for the era of 6G. Other future topics are to investigate the energy consumption of the XcARet solution itself, evaluate

the energy consumption of different ML models, and identify the places to make it more energy efficient through data reduction, efficient protocol design, and optimization of the utilized ML models.

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